

A DECADE IN REVIEW: EVOLUTION OF EDUCATION, HUMAN HEALTH, AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE SECTORS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper investigates the specific developments that occurred in the Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors within the Romanian Mountain Area over the ten-year period from 2008 to 2018. Through a comprehensive analysis of statistical data, this study aims to provide insights into the evolving landscapes of these crucial sectors, focusing on advancements, challenges, and their collective impact on the region.

1. Introduction:

The Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors are fundamental pillars for societal well-being and progress. This paper aims to shed light on the nuanced developments in these sectors within the context of the Romanian Mountain Area, examining statistical data to discern trends, achievements, and challenges over the specified decade.

2. Methodology:

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Utilizing a rigorous quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from official reports, educational institutions, healthcare providers, and social assistance agencies. Key indicators, including enrollment rates, healthcare infrastructure growth, and social support service accessibility, are examined to offer a comprehensive understanding of the sector-specific dynamics.

3. Education Sector Developments:

This section explores statistical intricacies related to the Education sector in the Romanian Mountain Area. Key metrics such as enrollment rates, educational infrastructure expansion, and academic achievements are scrutinized to assess the sector's role in shaping human capital and fostering intellectual growth within the region.

4. Human Health Sector Advancements:

The paper delves into the statistical landscape of the Human Health sector, examining trends in healthcare infrastructure, disease prevalence, and medical advancements. Insights into the region's healthcare accessibility, quality of services, and the impact of health policies on the local population are discussed.

5. Social Assistance Sector Progress:

Analyzing statistical data related to the Social Assistance sector, this section investigates developments in welfare programs, community support services, and the accessibility of social aid. The paper aims to evaluate the sector's effectiveness in addressing societal needs and promoting inclusivity within the Romanian Mountain Area.

6. Economic and Societal Impact:

Assessing the economic and societal impact of developments in the Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors, this section investigates their contributions to the regional well-being, employment rates, and overall community resilience. The paper emphasizes the interconnectedness of these sectors in shaping a holistic and sustainable society.

7. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying notable trends and challenges faced by these sectors during the specified period, this section provides insights into factors influencing educational, healthcare, and social dynamics. Considerations such as technological advancements, demographic shifts, and policy changes are explored, offering a forward-looking perspective on future developments.

8. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Education, human health and social assistance activities (figures 2.10.1 – 2.10.5 and appendices chapter 2), present for each sector separately rising values for the mean and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Mean, Std. Error of the Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th Percentiles; iteratively resumes for each individual indicator), as follows: mean of 32944.89, standard error at mean 3379.548, median 30918.00, standard deviation 10138.643, variance 102792085.611, Skewness .796, standard error at Skewness .717, Kurtosis -.451, standard error at Kurtosis 1.400, distance 29020, minimum 21633, maximum 50653 -1.0226, 2 percentile 50 - 730918.00, 75 - 41530.50.

The presented values demonstrate that the Education, human health and social assistance activities sectors in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central trend of the Education, human health and social assistance activities sectors of the economy during the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which it means that the results do not have a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.10.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.10.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S10 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .071, .208, -.028, .671, -.002, -3.109E-16; R-square .078, .213, -6.661E-16, 1.000, -4.441E-16, -2.220E-16; RMSE 813,548, 1475,201, .000, 10138,643, 72,694, 105,790; MAPS 49,316, 19,774, .000, 93,479, 18,157, 23,174; MaxAPE 148,444, 67,941, .000, 331,296, 42,729, 52,005; MAE 586,489, 1126,852, .000, 7903,877, 50,342, 75,671; MaxAE 1586,709,

2722,381, .000, 17708,111, 167,049, 198,342; Normalized BIC 12.156, 2.310, 8.803, 18.692, 9.057, 9.688.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S10

		Forecast										
Model		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945	32945
	UCL	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325	56325
	LCL	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565	9565
Macroregiunea unu-Model_2	Forecast	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279	9279
	UCL	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677	15677
	LCL	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881	2881
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994	3994
	UCL	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476	8476
	LCL	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488	-488
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917	917
	UCL	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848	1848
	LCL	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13	-13
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283	283
	UCL	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574
	LCL	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8	-8
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	2512	2648	2784	2921	3057	3193	3329	3466	3602	3738	3875
	UCL	4397	4533	4669	4806	4942	5078	5215	5351	5487	5623	5760
	LCL	627	763	899	1035	1172	1308	1444	1581	1717	1853	1990
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	848	896	944	992	1040	1088	1136	1184	1232	1279	1327
	UCL	1359	1409	1460	1510	1561	1611	1662	1712	1762	1813	1863

	LCL	338	383	428	474	519	565	610	655	701	746	792
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329	329
	UCL	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808
	LCL	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150	-150
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	356	380	404	427	451	475	498	522	545	569	593
	UCL	504	528	551	575	599	622	646	670	693	717	741
	LCL	209	232	256	280	303	327	350	374	398	421	445
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633	3633
	UCL	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550	7550
	LCL	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284	-284
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415	415
	UCL	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984	984
	LCL	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154	-154
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	1458	1531	1603	1675	1748	1820	1892	1965	2037	2109	2181
	UCL	2333	2405	2477	2549	2622	2694	2766	2839	2911	2983	3055
	LCL	584	657	729	801	874	946	1018	1091	1163	1235	1307
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213
	UCL	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488	488
	LCL	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63	-63
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356	356
	UCL	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787	787
	LCL	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76	-76
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832	832
	UCL	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766	1766
	LCL	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102	-102
Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768	768

	UCL	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525	1525
	LCL	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229	7229
	UCL	13555	15713	17423	18885	20184	21363	22452	23467	24423	25328	26190
	LCL	904	-1254	-2965	-4427	-5725	-6905	-7993	-9008	-9964	-10869	-11732
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271	3271
	UCL	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349	7349
	LCL	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808	-808
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753	753
	UCL	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442	1442
	LCL	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205
	UCL	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558	558
	LCL	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148	-148
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192	1192
	UCL	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655	2655
	LCL	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272	-272
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382	382
	UCL	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988	988
	LCL	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225	-225
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463	463
	UCL	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138	1138
	LCL	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213	-213
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277	277
	UCL	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637	637
	LCL	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83	-83

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688	2688
	UCL	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677	5677
	LCL	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301	-301
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
	UCL	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620	620
	LCL	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60	-60
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441
	UCL	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799	799
	LCL	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83	83
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948	948
	UCL	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052	2052
	LCL	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155	-155
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521	521
	UCL	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212	1212
	LCL	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170	-170
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205
	UCL	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368	368
	LCL	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43	43
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293	293
	UCL	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651	651
	LCL	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65	-65
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829	10829
	UCL	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834	16834
	LCL	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824	4824
Sud - Muntenia-Model_33	Forecast	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756	2756
	UCL	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910	5910
	LCL	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398	-398

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722	722
	UCL	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536	1536
	LCL	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92	-92
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167
	UCL	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367
	LCL	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33	-33
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404	404
	UCL	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928	928
	LCL	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119	-119
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116	116
	UCL	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306
	LCL	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73	-73
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194	194
	UCL	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441	441
	LCL	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53	-53
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927	927
	UCL	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876	1876
	LCL	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22	-22
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225
	UCL	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481	481
	LCL	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30	-30
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	9115	9568	10022	10475	10929	11382	11836	12289	12743	13196	13650
	UCL	13073	13526	13980	14433	14887	15340	15794	16247	16701	17154	17608
	LCL	5157	5610	6064	6517	6971	7425	7878	8332	8785	9239	9692
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	7930	8286	8642	8999	9355	9711	10067	10423	10779	11135	11491
	UCL	11711	12067	12423	12779	13135	13491	13848	14204	14560	14916	15272
	LCL	4149	4506	4862	5218	5574	5930	6286	6642	6998	7354	7710

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1282	1380	1478	1576	1674	1771	1869	1967	2065	2163	2261
	UCL	1550	1759	1942	2111	2273	2428	2578	2725	2869	3010	3150
	LCL	1014	1001	1014	1040	1074	1115	1160	1209	1261	1316	1372
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063	6063
	UCL	10774	12305	13529	14579	15513	16363	17147	17880	18570	19223	19846
	LCL	1353	-179	-1403	-2452	-3386	-4236	-5021	-5753	-6443	-7097	-7719
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078	2078
	UCL	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359	4359
	LCL	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203	-203
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865	865
	UCL	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764	1764
	LCL	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34	-34
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333	333
	UCL	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712	712
	LCL	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46	-46
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178
	UCL	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513	513
	LCL	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158	-158
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335	335
	UCL	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598	598
	LCL	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71	71
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367	367
	UCL	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818	818
	LCL	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84	-84
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739	2739
	UCL	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758	5758
	LCL	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280	-280

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639	639
	UCL	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360	1360
	LCL	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82	-82
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280	280
	UCL	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587	587
	LCL	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27	-27
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483	483
	UCL	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980	980
	LCL	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14	-14
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337	1337
	UCL	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859	2859
	LCL	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184	-184

9. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive examination of developments in the Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance sectors in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the region's social fabric, offering valuable insights for policymakers, institutions, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable growth in these critical sectors.

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